

Strategies for conservation of wildlife and endangered species

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Introduction

In feeding and laboratory animals, reproductive technologies have been used for more than a century. In order to sustain specialized biomedical research models in laboratory species and to increase production yield in farm animals, it has been essential to be able to reproduce desirable genetic features. Humans are the primary beneficiaries of the outcomes in both of these examples, including the provision of dietary supplies and medical treatments to support the health and well-being of a growing worldwide population. The unprecedented increase in the human population and the ensuing need for both natural and man-made resources, however, has led to a rapid and continuous loss in the world's biodiversity. Conservation programme managers are realizing the significance of adopting assisted reproductive technologies (ARTs) to improve reproductive performance and guarantee the long-term preservation of rich genetic resources as more vertebrate species approach extinction. However, routinely implementing these technologies has been challenging, and the proportion of live births attributable to ARTs does not accurately represent the significant efforts made thus far. The success and difficulties of creating ARTs for species with a wide range of reproductive architecture, mating behavior, and natural life histories are the main strategies.

Technologies for species conservation

A) Reproductive technologies: The long-term preservation of priceless and rare alleles is the top priority of conservation breeding initiatives, that is, ex situ propagation of threatened and endangered animals. The current technique keeps 90% of the genetic variety of wildlife populations kept in zoos and breeding facilities over a century. There are many obstacles in the way of this strategy, which ideally calls for maintaining a minimum number of animals to prevent inbreeding

and the loss of unique alleles, as well as equitable representation of all founders in the captive population. Natural breeding does not always succeed in maintaining heterozygosity, frequently as a result of the breeding pair's sexual incompatibility or the difficulties of moving the animals between geographically far areas. Numerous publications on the use of ARTs in wildlife species have gone into great length about the methods used, such as ovarian hormone monitoring and modification and gamete/embryo cryopreservation.

1) Artificial insemination: The most useful form of art for wildlife species is AI. It is believed that AI (with or without hormone induction) has been the most effective method for obtaining consistent pregnancy and live birth rates because to the technological simplicity and low level of invasiveness (for most species). Because of improvements in cattle, AI was first used on wild ungulates. The routine use of this assisted breeding technique is only permitted for animal species that are managed for commercial purposes, such as red deer, fallow deer, white-tailed deer, and reindeer, despite positive results in more than 50 species. ARTs have only been included in the breeding management plans of a small number of conservation species. A variety of species have experienced some substantial successes as a result of the significant time and effort invested in them, but each poses different difficulties for the species' long-term maintenance under human care.

Giant panda (*Ailuropoda melanoleuca*): In breeding facilities around the world, AI has been utilized to overcome behavioral incompatibility, resulting in the birth of numerous cubs. Birth rates after artificial insemination of natural cycles are roughly one-third lower than those achieved by natural mating (18.5% vs. 60.7%), according to a recent review of 304 artificial insemination attempts over 21 years.

Asian (*Elephas maximus*) and African elephant (*Loxodonta africana*): The insemination of Asian elephants (*Elephas maximus*) and African elephants (*Loxodonta africana*) has advanced significantly as a result of the necessity to enhance genetic management while minimising breeding-related transfers of huge mega-vertebrates between institutions.

There has been a lot of improvement in nonmammalian species compared to the scant advancement in mammalian species. Since the 1970s, AI in wild birds has been well-documented, and it has been crucial in the captive breeding of species like cranes (*sandhill cranes, Grus canadensis; whooping cranes, Grus americana*), raptors, and owls (*golden eagle, Aquila chrysaetos; Peregrine falcon, Falco peregrinus; American kestrel, Falco sparverius*). The majority of these instances involved the use of AI to improve the reproductive health and genetic management of the small confined populations.

2) In vitro fertilization: Due to increasing threats to natural areas and a decline in global biodiversity, many species are vanishing before any efforts to protect their genetic material may be successful. Modern methods for producing gametes and embryos have successfully utilized cryopreserved somatic and stem cells. Most significantly, ocelot (*Leopardus pardalis*) in vitro embryo development is being explored as a long-term genetic management technique for captive ocelot populations. There have been numerous attempts to create mammalian embryos in vitro, either by IVF or ICSI, in a wide variety of wildlife species utilising culture techniques developed for a related model species, with different degrees of success, thanks to the knowledge obtained from related domesticated species.

B) Emerging technologies: Many species are going extinct before any efforts to conserve their genetic material may be successful due to ongoing threats to natural areas and a reduction in global biodiversity. Cryopreserved somatic and stem cells were successfully used in cutting-edge techniques to create gametes and embryos.

1) Cell transplantation technologies: The ability to permanently maintain the genetic material from dangerous and endangered animal species may change if primordial germ cell (PGC) transplantation is used. PGCs are the forerunners of functional gametes (e.g., sperm or eggs). In order to develop germ line chimaeras that can finally produce a functional donor gamete and pass on the entire genetic information to the next generation, this approach entails injecting isolated PGCs of a rare species into an embryo of a more common counterpart.

2) Spermatogonial stem cell (SSC) transplantation: SSCs are the building blocks of spermatogenesis and arise from gonocytes in the postnatal testis. SSCs produce haploid spermatozoa and are capable of self-renewal and differentiation. After the transfer of embryos created by microinjecting sperm generated from SSCs that had been stored for 14 years, viable offspring have been produced in the mouse. SSC transplanting has thus far been investigated in mammals, birds, and aquatic species with some encouraging outcomes.

3) Somatic cell technologies: The utilization of induced pluripotent stem cells technology to create iPSC-derived germ cells, which might subsequently be combined with other ART, holds enormous potential for the rescue and preservation of priceless genomes as well as therapeutic applications for animals suffering from degenerative diseases.

4) Gonadal tissue cryopreservation: Various wildlife species, such as the wombat (*Vombatus ursinus*), African elephant (*L. africana*), tammar wallaby (*Macropus eugenii*), lion (*P. leo*), Amur leopard (*Panthera pardus orientalis*), black-footed cat (*F. nigripes*), Geoffroy's cat (*Leopardus geoffroyi*). Routine cryopreservation of ovarian tissue has also been recorded in a different group of

endangered animals, such as the black-footed ferret (*M. nigripes*), cheetah (*Acinonyx jubatus*), clouded leopard (*N. nebulosa*), scimitar-horned oryx (*Oryx dammah*), and Eld's deer (*Rucervus eldii*).

Conclusion

Wildlife breeding management objectives are somewhat comparable to those of other industries, like the food and laboratory animal sectors. Population managers face enormous pressure to achieve breeding success due to the requirement to reproduce specific people in order to secure the retention of their alleles in current and future populations, underscoring the significance of implementation. Current anthropogenic pressures continue to pose a threat to the survival of wildlife species. It is time for specialists from zoological, academic, governmental, and other institutions to work together more closely in order to focus on a single objective: the long-term preservation of the genetic diversity of wildlife species that still exists in the world. In order to help with the difficulties of satisfying animal welfare standards, it is crucial to maintain support for the inclusion of ARTs as standard tools in animal management programmes.

